

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D 8.5: Urban waste management

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from (March 2025) to (September 2025)
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Milestone 8.1 Responsible	Prof. Paolo Esposito
RM8 Responsible	Prof. Paolo Esposito

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

List of Deliverables

#	Name	Type		Due month	Due date	Short description	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
D8.1	Waste management in the context of public administration	R	PU	12	18/03/2024	Report containing data related waste management creating public value developed in the frame of the project and prepared from emerging public services practices		04/04/2024
D8.2	Defining clear objectives and measuring them by using appropriate indicators	R	PU	18	30/09/2024	Report containing appropriate indicators related waste management creating public value		03/10/2024
D8.3	Methodology and training contents based on social impact	R	PU	24	31/03/2025	Report containing methodological approach		01/04/2025
D8.4	Case Study applied to waste management	R	PU	28	30/09/2025	Report containing case studies on waste management creating public value developed in the frame of the project and prepared from emerging		30/09/2025

						public services practices	
D8.5	Urban waste management	R	PU	30	30/09/2025	Report containing standards on: - process improvement and measurement design for the public investments in waste Management; - measurement of social impact between citizen and municipalities to create Public Value.	30/09/2025

List of Milestone

#	Name	Type	Due month	Due date	Short description	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
M1	Analysis of the state of art	Report	10 (Gennaio 2024)	04/02/2024	The investigation of the legal framework.		04/02/2024
M2	Defining the main Stakeholder Mapping	Report	12	18/03/2024	The investigation of the Stakeholder Mapping		04/04/2024
M3	Defining the main social impact and measuring public value creation	Report	18	30/09/2024	The investigation of the legal framework		30/09/2024

A) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

1. Introduction

1.1 Objective of the Deliverable

Deliverable D5 entitled "Urban waste management" is started in March 2025, at the achievement of the D3 named "Methodology and training contents based on social impact".

1.2 Context

The Research Team is composed by Professor Paolo Esposito, Arturo Capasso, Maria Moreno, Riccardo Resciniti, Guido Tortorella and Matteo Rossi.

Other Member of the Research Team are: Ahmad Zubair, till 30/06/2025, and Ciuffreda Raffaella, Research Fellow.

2. Urban Waste Management Standards and Guidelines

This task reveals that encouraging waste management not only helps cities reduce risks, but also reduces the burden on cities to dispose of a huge volume of municipal waste in landfills. This makes cities climate resilient and promotes the concept of a sustainable and resilient city, which is one of the strengths of the project.

The task intends to produce new standards and guidelines in the urban waste management on:

- process improvement and measurement design for the public investments in waste management;
- measurement of social impact between citizens, companies and municipalities to create public value.

2.1. Public Value in Public Services

Over the past two decades, research on public value (PV) has increased significantly within public administration and management, solidifying its place as a key focus in both academic and managerial discourse related to the delivery of public services (Van Der Wal, Nabatchi, & De Graaf, 2015; Osborne et al., 2016; John et al., 2017).

A growing body of literature calls for a deeper understanding of public value creation (O'Cass & Ngo, 2011; Voorberg et al., 2015), stressing the importance of aligning the needs and expectations of service users with organizational goals. This shift calls for an actor-to-actor approach, focusing not just on inter-organizational relationships but also on the interactions between public service organizations and citizens (Osborne et al., 2015; Skålén et al., 2018). This actor-centric view is crucial in the contemporary public management

landscape, where all actors—including citizens—are seen as resource integrators and co-creators of value (Akaka et al., 2013; Maijala et al., 2024). Already Moore (2013, p. 9) denoted “the procedural question of what actors (working through what processes) could legitimize a particular concept of public value and the substantive question of which particular values this legitimate actor would choose”. Moreover, Osborne, Nasi and Powell (2021) have elaborated the model regarding the processes of public value creation for public services and they admitted “the existence of multiple stakeholders with potentially varying perspective on the value created by a public service” (Osborne et al., 2021; p. 652). Nevertheless, they have not identified the various stakeholders.

In the context of urban waste management, theories of effectuation (Brown, 2012) and co-production indicate that public service organizations must navigate uncertainty by transforming initial ideas into sustainable solutions, utilizing available resources and expertise to co-create public value. Nonetheless, as highlighted by Steen et al. (2018), co-production may also perpetuate inequalities or erode stakeholder trust, leading to the emergence of public disvalue. This is evident in sectors such as cultural services, where unmet expectations or failure to address diverse societal needs can lead to dissatisfaction (Hartley et al., 2019). Moreover, corruption perception and trust in institutions act as mediators in the manifestation of public disvalue (Esposito et al., 2025).

Encouraging integrated and participatory approaches to waste management not only contributes to the reduction of urban risks but also alleviates the pressure on municipal landfills. This contributes to enhancing urban climate resilience and aligns with the broader vision of a sustainable and resilient city—one of the key strengths of the project.

2.2. Insight from Case Study

Previous case studies by Ferronato et al. (2016) explore an interdisciplinary approach to integrated solid waste management in La Paz, Bolivia, highlighting the need for waste management systems in developing countries. A recent case study by Goren et al. (2023) analyzes solid waste management in Makkah, Saudi Arabia, focusing on local challenges and practices. Both case studies provide valuable insights into waste management systems within their respective contexts. However, neither study comprehensively delves into the role and impact of diverse stakeholders involved in waste management processes. The findings of the A.S.I.A. Benevento S.p.A. case study underscore the collaboration among diverse actors to enhance public value creation.

The researchers divide the multiple stakeholders into 5 main categories, as Caniato et al. (2014):

1. Governmental Authorities: this group includes various policymakers, local health authorities, chambers of commerce, and both local and national governmental organizations. Their primary role involves the development and enforcement of regulations and laws that establish guidelines for public and private sector operations.
2. Private Sector: trade associations, professional associations and industrial federation have a vital role in driving economic growth and ensuring financial sustainability. These entities are focused on enhancing their economic outcomes while delivering quality services to the community.

3. **Academia:** this category consists of universities and research centres that are pivotal in fostering knowledge and innovation. They engage in scholarly research and offer training programs designed to equip future leaders and professionals with the necessary skills and capabilities.
4. **Civil Society:** encompassing a wide array of citizens, employees, and volunteers play a crucial role in advocating for public awareness, promoting public health initiatives, and protecting the environment. Their efforts aim to engage citizens and drive social change.
5. **Other Stakeholders:** this category includes a diverse group of participants who may not fit neatly into the aforementioned categories but have important roles in the broader ecosystem, such as the Public Prosecutor's Offices, the Division of Carabinieri for the Prevention of the Adulteration of Food and Drink; Prefecture and so on.

As waste management continues to evolve, understanding these dynamics will be essential for policymakers aiming to balance efficiency with equity in public service delivery. Future research should further explore the implications of these findings across different contexts and sectors, providing deeper insights into effective public service management practices. In conclusion, Public Service Logic offers a valuable lens through which to examine the complexities of public value creation or destruction in public services.

2.3. Organizational Models and Multi-Level Governance in Italian Urban Waste Management

Waste management is not an exception concerning the measurement of public value, and accounting continues to play a central role in the process. Accountability plays a critical role in ensuring that public value is effectively created and sustained (Cruz Dallagnol et al. 2023). Proper accounting for waste management activities helps in keeping a record of the cost and value or gain that could be achieved from practising waste management (Romano, Masserini, and Lombardi 2021). The economic, social, and environmental consequences of waste management can be determined by following the strategies of the Triple Bottom Line framework suggested by Elkington (1997). By structures of governance, it means that waste management is determined by governance structures to a large extent. This paper evaluates how decentralized governance can enhance waste management and reports that local authorities and communities can enhance waste management results. For instance, research has shown that the waste management decentralized system in Italy has recorded higher performance as compared to the centralized waste management systems (Beck and Ferasso 2023).

The research design covers the Italian case study, where waste cycle management service is operated at a local level through totally publicly owned companies, mixed companies, or via a complete externalization achieved utilizing public tenders. The choice of this country is justified by the relevance of the urban waste management issue: indeed, the per capita waste production is undeniably higher than the European average. The service of waste cycle management is operated in Italy at the local level “through totally public owned companies (mono-administration or multiadministrations), mixed companies (public-private), or full externalization through public tender” (Esposito et al., 2021a; p. 1070). Waste management in public administration is a paradigmatic example of a local

public service affecting social, environmental, and financial sustainability (Tafuro et al., 2022).

The municipal waste management sector is characterized by multi-level governance, in which different institutional actors intervene at various levels and with different competencies (Esposito et al., 2021b). The regulation of the service is entrusted to ARERA (Energy Networks and Environment Regulatory Authority), which, following the entry into force of Law 205/17, acquired specific competencies in the field of economic and tariff regulation in order to establish a clear and uniform regulatory framework that stimulates the actors operating in the sector to improve service levels, contributing to the achievement of the environmental objectives set by European and national legislation. ARERA is part of a context in which the competencies related to waste management are divided among the Ministry, the Regions, the Provinces, the Municipalities and the sphere government bodies. These entities play roles ranging from general policy and coordination to operational and organisational management linked to the specific needs of the local territory. Based on data from the ARERA report (2024), the national average of separate waste collection reached 65.2% in 2022 (+ 1.2 percentage points compared to 2021), while 17.8% of the municipal waste produced ends up in landfills. At the level of geographical areas, the North also ranks first (71.8%), followed by the Centre (61.5%) and the South (57.7%).

The management of urban waste has been a topic of significant debate globally, as it constitutes a critical factor influencing the environmental quality of any nation and a great challenge for the pursuit of sustainable development (Chen et al., 2014; Peltola et al., 2016). The significance of the waste sector has grown within local government operations, largely as a result of increasing public awareness regarding environmental matters and the impact these issues have on fiscal policies (Esposito et al., 2024).

2.4. Ethical Dilemmas

Ethical issues always occur as a result of the clash of interests and values in the process of performing waste management duties. These are usually dilemmas that pertain to the management of resources, matters affecting the ecology, and the position of future generations (Alberti and Belfanti 2019). These dilemmas can only be resolved if one appreciates the ethical consequences of waste management (Bracci et al. 2019). Those ethical challenges have been responded to by theoretical frameworks such as the Environmental Justice Theory or Sustainability Ethics. Environmental Justice Theory aims to put into consideration the equitable shares of the environmental highlights; highlighting the need to save endangered groups of people. Sustainability Ethics stress the ethical obligation not to diminish the future generations' capability to fulfil their want (Garbani-Nerini et al. 2024).

2.5. Planning, Financing, and Promoting Sustainability Policies

There is a need for proper planning and financing in the management of waste within society for sustainability. To make waste management successful, long-term planning should be done and the firm should link with other industries while developing a special

fund for waste management (Dreyfus et al. 2010). It is to be documented that cities focusing on a proper management plan for waste and having long-term innovation can establish good results (Leder, Kumar and Rodrigues, 2020; Villani and Greco, 2016). Sometimes, in addition to declaring such principles and implementing safety measures, it is crucial to raise the awareness of the population on these issues and change people's behaviours (Barrutia et al., 2022). In encouraging sustainability, the use of education campaigns involving encouraging the lawmakers to provide incentives for more recycling and the use of regulations were considered. Studies have established that such programmes affect the extent of the inclination of citizens towards positive change in the level of compliance with waste management and the intensity of sustainability aspirations (Esposito, Dicorato, and Doronzo, 2021).

2.6. Impact on Individual Freedom

Waste management practices can impact individual liberty and the city form. It can be stated that regulations that reduce the possibilities of waste disposal or force recycling are invasive of personal freedom (Bottausci et al. 2022). However, such policies are usually needed to attain public value objectives. Factors such as the accessibility of waste bins and recycling points included in the urban design have an impact on the efficiency of waste management strategies (Beck et al. 2023). Thus, in weighing the public value against the rights and freedoms of the individual, waste management policies need to show both the advantages and the disadvantages. To balance these views, people should be involved in making policies and acknowledging the public the necessity of management of waste (Fusco and Allegrini 2020).

3. Economic implications

From an economic perspective, to realize the full economic potential of public-private collaboration in urban waste management, public authorities should establish rigorous regulatory frameworks that clearly delineate roles, responsibilities, and performance expectations for all partners. These frameworks must include transparent procurement procedures, well-defined service standards, and enforceable contractual provisions to prevent profit-driven priorities from undermining service quality or inflating costs. At the same time, trade associations and industry federations ought to participate in the co-creation of financing models that balance market viability with affordability for municipalities. Academia should be engaged from the outset to design evidence-based metrics and deliver targeted training, ensuring that both public agencies and private contractors possess the analytical tools and technical expertise required to optimize infrastructure investments. Regular economic impact assessments, co-authored by government, industry, and academic stakeholders, will verify that private-sector contributions generate genuine public value without shifting undue financial risk onto taxpayers.

4. Social Implications

From a social standpoint, nurturing social value through collaborative waste-

management practices begin with embedding community needs assessments into every project phase. Municipalities should convene civil society organizations, neighborhood associations, and citizen advocates to articulate local priorities—whether related to health, environmental justice, or resource access—and translate these priorities into measurable social-impact objectives. Public agencies must allocate dedicated funding for awareness campaigns and capacity-building workshops that equip residents with the knowledge and skills to sort, reduce, and repurpose waste effectively. To track progress toward the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 11.6 on air quality and waste reduction and SDG 12.5 on waste prevention and reuse, participating organizations should adopt standardized social-impact indicators and publish progress reports in accessible formats. Finally, co-design mechanisms that solicit ongoing resident feedback will identify emerging inequalities or unintended environmental harms, enabling agile course corrections before social value erodes.

5. Political Implications

From a political angle, ensuring that political oversight strengthens rather than impedes waste-management innovation requires the adoption of governance protocols centered on transparency, accountability, and stakeholder inclusion. Local health authorities, environmental regulators, and municipal decision-makers should jointly craft participatory policy forums where representatives from government, industry, and community groups can review performance data and deliberate on strategic adjustments. Anti-corruption safeguards—such as third-party audits, conflict-of-interest disclosures, and public procurement tribunals—must be embedded within all contractual arrangements to guard against value co-destruction. Equally important is the institution of formal risk-assessment processes that identify potential sources of public disvalue—ranging from policy loopholes to operational failures—and prescribe mitigation measures. Open communication channels, including regularly scheduled town halls and digital dashboards, will sustain public trust by making policymakers' decisions and service outcomes visible to every stakeholder.

6. Key Challenges and Opportunities in Waste Management

The main issue with waste management in This is that its share of organic waste is relatively large and reaches approximately 30% of the overall municipal waste (Carrasco et al. 2021). Since there is an increase in the generation of organic waste, proper management of this waste will help to reduce the use of landfills or manage their usage to minimize greenhouse gas emissions (Agovino et al. 2018). Other issues include poor disposal, which not only has environmental implications but also financial implications since it increases the spending of the municipality. However, it is also possible to identify some improvements regarding waste management systems in This. These are already strong in most cities today and the recycling infrastructure of many cities is already well-developed (Bertossi, Kaulard, and Massarutto 2000). Also, Smart Bins and Waste-to-Energy Technologies present the prospect for growth, as they ensure the waste is better managed and collected (Minervini 2022).

Carrasco, Javier, Elisa López, Manuel Guillamón, and Fidel Salas. (2021). "An Overview about

the Current Situation on C&D Waste Management in Italy: Achievements and Challenges.” *Buildings* 11 (7). <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-5309/11/7/284>.

7. Further research and Limitations

The NODES' research is completed and achieved. In this sense, further analysis will push us to critically examine several key elements: accounting and governance systems, impacts and implications for individual freedom of movement, planning, financing and promotion of sustainability policies. Furthermore, the implications for public administrations can include optimizing environmental impact, promoting sustainability, and contributing to the circular economy.

This research is not without limitations. It is based on a single case study, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other contexts. Furthermore, it primarily focuses on the waste management sector in a specific geographic area, leaving room to explore how waste management impacts public value in other regions or countries. To address these limitations, future research should adopt a comparative approach, analysing multiple waste management sites to assess how public value is created or destroyed through waste management practices across diverse institutional, socio-economic, and technological contexts.

8. Some Publications during NODES' research project

1. Esposito, P., Doronzo, E., Riso, V., & Tufo, M. (2025). Sustainability in energy companies under the lens of cultural pressures: when do we talk of greenwashing?. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 32 (3), 3814-3831. Wiley Online Library, New York, USA. ISSN:1535-3966, Print ISSN:1535-3958. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.3111> [Rivista di Classe A ANVUR/ASN (Q1 e ABS1)].
2. Esposito, P., & Tufo, M. (2025). Beyond Crisis: How to Measure Public Value in a National Recovery Plan. In Vrontis et al. (eds.), *Business in a Turbulent Era, Volume II: Technology, Society, and Policy* (pp. 135-161). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland. Print ISBN: 978-3-031-89805-1, Online ISBN: 978-3-031-89806-8. ISSN: 2523-8167; ISSN: 2523-8175 (electronic). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-89806-8_6 Scopus-listed Book Series “Palgrave Studies in Cross-disciplinary Business Research, In Association with EuroMed Academy of Business”.
3. Esposito, P., & Tufo, M. (2025). Public Value Creation in Sustainable Tourism: Multiple Case Studies of Cultural Organisations. In Vrontis D. et al., *Exploring New Horizons in Business and Management* (p. 1040). 18th Annual Conference of the EuroMed Academy of Business, Euromed Press, Cyprus. ISSN: 2547-8516, ISBN: 978-9925-628-05-6.
4. Esposito, P., & Tufo, M. (2025). Implementing Sustainable PPPs: Safeguarding Public Value in Motorway. *Sustainable and Socially Responsible Development in the Network of*

Socioeconomic Relations. Annual Conference, WSB Merito University in Gdansk, Poland.
June 16-17, 2025
https://drive.google.com/file/d/1EKenyaJ31yAkynpX4aotCboNTvrWg5_/view

5. Esposito, P., Tufo, M., Rossi, P., & Boggio, G. (2024). Unlocking Italy's potential: measuring public value in a national Recovery Plan. In Vrontis D. et al., *Global Business Transformation in a Turbulent Era* (p. 809). 17th Annual Conference of the EuroMed Academy of Business, Euromed Press, Cyprus. ISSN: 2547-8516, ISBN: 978-9925-628-01-8.
6. Fiorani, G., Di Gerio, G., Doronzo, E., & Tufo, M. (2025). Accounting and Stakeholder Engagement through Non-Financial Reporting Practices: Public Value in the Italian Waste Sector. SIDREA International Workshop (SIW) "Public (dis)value accounting and accountability: a stakeholder theory perspective". University of Naples "Parthenope", Villa Doria D'Angri, Naples, Italy, 26 Maggio 2025.
7. Ahmad, Z., & Tufo, M. (2025). Enhancing Public Value through Sustainable Waste Management: A Comprehensive Analysis. SIDREA International Workshop (SIW) "Public (dis)value accounting and accountability: a stakeholder theory perspective". University of Naples "Parthenope", Villa Doria D'Angri, Naples, Italy, 26 Maggio 2025.
8. Esposito, P., & Tufo, M., (2025). Stakeholder Mapping for Public Value through Assetization in Waste Management, IRSPM (International Research Society in Public Management) Annual Conference 2025, University of Bologna "Alma Mater Studiorum", Bologna, Italy, 7th-9th April 2025.
9. Esposito P., Tufo M., Rossi P., & Boggio G. (2024). Retracing public value creation through digital and sustainable transformation. A Recovery Plan case study. EGPA PSG XII 2024 Spring Workshop, University of Basilicata, Matera, Italy, May 9th-10th 2024.
10. Esposito, P., & Tufo, M. (2024). Measuring public value in NODES Project. Mapping a theoretical framework. XVI Riunione Scientifica della Società Italiana di Scienze del Turismo (SISTUR) "Prospettive e tendenze del turismo, fra viaggi, identità culturali ed ospitalità". Palazzo Mediceo, Ottaviano (Napoli), 31 Ottobre - 2 novembre 2024.